

OVERVIEW OF THE EU INNOVATION INTERMEDIARIES' AND PUBLIC AGENCIES FUNCTIONS

The innovation system is self-organizing and co-evolving (Lundvall 2007), but the functions of institutions and the actors shaping it are decisive for its operation (Martin & Scott 2000). In this context, increasing learning and innovation capacity means not only spending more resources on education and research, but also creating a wide range of institutions to support interactive learning (Cooke 2001; Lundvall 2007) and knowledge dissemination (Feinson 2003) in all parts of society, including individual families, communities, firms, and organizations. More attention should be focused on the processes of communication and cooperation between innovation actors, where economically useful knowledge is created and applied (Lundvall 2007). The coordination of market and non-market agents (Maloney 2017) and public and private actors (Coenen et al. 2016) through the formation of appropriate networks (Feinson 2003), is necessary to ensure the application and diffusion of innovation. Such networks do not appear automatically but require state incentives to create formal and informal institutions that facilitate the exchange of information, training and advisory activities, subcontracting, standards development, etc. (Feinson 2003). Thus, the state's function of the formation of links and relationships becomes of critical importance. Klerkx & Leeuwis (2009) argue that the state could realize its coordinating role through the creation of innovation intermediaries. Innovation intermediaries are important elements of the functioning of an effective innovation system, as they support companies and provide knowledge and technology flows between science and business (Daniluk 2017). At the same time, the functions and organizational forms of such organizations are manifold, represented by business and innovation centers, non-bank financial institutions, etc. (Daniluk 2017, 129). The government's leading role in the creation of innovation intermediaries is due to the complexity of ensuring the self-sufficiency of demand articulation and network formation activities, the catalyzing role of intermediaries, and the need to be neutral yet compliant with the state's objectives while supporting the innovators (Klerkx & Leeuwis 2009). The existing state funding institutions, advisory organizations in agriculture, as well as systems of technological and scientific information, present only certain functions of an innovation intermediary organization; the single structure approach is absent in Ukraine. Certain networks of business and SME development organizations, supported by international institutions (in particular, "UnlimitUkraine"¹, "EU4business"²) partially deal with issues of innovation development as well. In this context, the creation of a single body responsible for implementing the state innovation policy is crucial for the efficient functioning of the NIS in Ukraine. It will ensure a single vision and maintain basic goals and principles at all stages of the innovation process. Given the variety of possible organizational forms and functions of innovative intermediaries (Daniluk 2017; Klerkx & Leeuwis 2009), it is advisable to investigate the European experience in this area, especially in view of Ukraine's European integration commitment.

A state-reporting agency responsible for implementing the innovation policy has been established in almost every EU country; however, they differ in the organizational, legal and ownership forms, as well as their activities. Most of them provide the entire spectrum of functional activities within the IS framework (e.g. business support, the development and dissemination of knowledge, demand articulation, funding, and the innovation policy formation (Wieczorek & Hekkert 2012), thus acting as innovation intermediaries. Therefore, a close study of the organizational and legal bases, as well as the functions of such agencies, is expedient in order to determine the model that will best suit Ukraine.

Analysis of the information presented on the agencies' official web pages allows us to distinguish several models, namely: 1) The Ministries conducting educational and economic policy jointly create and control the agency's activities (Table 1); 2) The agency primarily reports to the Ministry responsible for the economic policy (Table 2); 3) The agency mainly reports to the Ministry responsible for the educational policy; and others.

¹ <http://unlimitukraine.com.ua/> (accessed: 10.09.2018)

² <http://www.eu4business.eu/uk/smeprojects> (accessed: 10.09.2018)

Table 1. National agencies of innovation development under the joint control of Ministries, responsible for the educational and economic policy

Agency (country, web-page)	Activities performed												
	Funding R&D projects	Science-business	Knowledge transfer	Policy promotion	International cooperation	Export support	SME support	Training	Advisory services	Funding educational	Regional programs	Investment attraction	Network (inside/abroad)
ANI (Portugal, www.ani.pt)	+	+	+	+	+								
Luxinnovation (Luxembourg, www.luxinnovation.lu/)		+	+	+	+		+	+	+			+	
MITA (Lithuania, https://mita.lrv.lt)	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+			+	
Innosuisse (Switzerland, www.innosuisse.ch **)	+	+	+				+	+	+				+/+
VLAIO (Belgium, www.vlaio.be **)	+	+		+			+			+			+

** A single department is responsible for economic development, research and scientific policies

Source: authors' investigation.

The given data (Tables 1, 2) show that most innovation agencies in EU countries primarily report to the Ministry that conducts economic policy. The functions of such organizations are quite broad and cover, in particular, training and consulting services for business, the development of science-business cooperation, the funding of business innovative projects, as well as the promotion of innovation and regional policy, etc. These organizations tend to have an extensive network within the country and even abroad (for example, in Finland, Estonia, Ireland, Italy, Spain, Croatia, and Switzerland).

The number of organizations created by the Ministry responsible for the educational policy is limited, as are their functions. For instance, the Danish Agency for Institutions and Educational Grants³ is responsible only for the promotion policy and for funding educational programs. Innovation Fund Serbia⁴ is empowered to finance R&D and to attract investments.

In some countries, there is no single agency, but separate organizations operate which report to the bodies responsible for the educational policy and the economic development policy. The Research Council of Norway⁵ reports to the Ministry responsible for the educational policy and deals with funding innovative projects, funding educational projects, promoting education policy, science, and business cooperation, international cooperation issues, attracting investment and it has a well-developed network of offices. Another organization – Innovation Norway⁶ – reports to the Ministry responsible for economic policy, and implements activities aimed at supporting all stages of the innovation process (except for financing educational and regional projects) and attracting investment. This Ministry also has an extensive network within the country and abroad. The Ministry of Education, Science, and Culture in Iceland coordinates the activities of “Rannis”⁷. The organization is responsible for funding innovative projects, including educational and scientific institutions' R&D, policy promotion, attracting

³ <https://ufm.dk/en/the-ministry/organisation/danish-agency-for-institutions-and-educational-grants/> (accessed: 02.09.2018)

⁴ <http://www.innovationfund.rs/> (accessed: 02.09.2018)

⁵ <https://www.forskningradet.no/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

⁶ <https://www.innovasjon Norge.no/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

⁷ <http://www.rannis.is/english/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

investment, and international cooperation. On the other hand, the Ministry of Industry and Innovation empowers Innovation Center Iceland⁸ to promote science and business cooperation, to provide knowledge transfer to companies, to support SMEs, to provide training and consulting, and to attract investments.

Table 2. National agencies of innovation development under the control of the Ministry conducting economic policy

Agency (country, web-page)	Activities performed												
	Funding R&D projects	Science-business	Knowledge transfer	Policy promotion	International cooperation	Export support	SME support	Training	Advisory services	Funding educational	Regional programs	Investment attraction	Network (inside/abroad)
CDTI (Spain, www.cdti.es/)	+		+	+	+								+/+
ENEA (Italy, www.enea.it)	+	+	+	+	+				+		+		+/+
HAMAG-BICRO, Croatia, www.investcroatia.hr/	+	+					+		+	+		+	+/+
NRDI Office (Hungary, www.nkfi.gov.hu/the-office/)	+			+	+					+			
Netherlands Enterprise Agency, www.english.rvo.nl	+	+	+	+	+							+	+
Slovak Innovation and Energy Agency, www.en.siea.sk/		+	+	+	+	+		+	+		+	+	
SPIRIT (Slovenia, www.spiritslovenia.si)		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			+	
FFG* (Austria, www.ffg.at)	+	+		+	+				+	+			
Agency for Entrepreneurship and Innovation (the Czech Republic, www.agentura-api.org)	+			+	+		+	+	+			+	
Business Finland (Finland, www.businessfinland.fi)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+						+/+
Enterprise Estonia (Estonia, www.eas.ee)	+				+	+		+	+		+		+/+
Enterprise Ireland (Ireland, www.enterprise-ireland.com)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+				+/+
PARP (the Republic of Poland, www.en.parp.gov.pl)	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vinnova (Sweden, www.vinnova.se)	+	+								+			

** also created with the participation of the Ministry responsible for transport, innovation and technology policies*

Source: authors' investigation.

⁸ <https://www.nmi.is/en/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

The intermediary organizations operating in Germany, France, the United Kingdom, and Turkey have a slightly different model. For instance, the German infrastructure for promoting innovation is extensive and well developed. It involves several dozen organizations that are both private (Project Management Jülich⁹) and public-private (The High-Tech Gründerfonds¹⁰, German Center for Research and Innovation¹¹). These organizations support innovators and research institutions, actively collaborate with the government, research and business entities, and give full-fledged support to innovation and related policy development. The State Financial Institution “Bpifrance”¹² supports innovation diffusion and implementation in France, ensuring R&D funding and international cooperation, assisting export-oriented companies and SMEs, promoting regional development projects and it also attracts investments. Innovate UK¹³, as a non-departmental public body, reports to the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, which coordinates the activities of 14 different ministries in the UK. The organization promotes innovation development through financing R&D, strengthening science-business cooperation, and ensuring the transfer of knowledge to companies. The TTGV¹⁴ is a non-profit innovation intermediary organization in Turkey, operating on the basis of a public-private partnership. It gives full-fledged support to innovation development and appropriate policy, excluding the funding of educational projects.

Given the existing EU experience, it makes sense to establish an appropriate state-coordinated agency in Ukraine in order to provide an innovation-based development of society. This institution should, in our opinion, ensure the efficient implementation of policies in the field of innovation and entrepreneurship as well as regional development, since they are interconnected. The organizational peculiarities and the set of its functions are described below.

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⁹ <https://www.ptj.de> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

¹⁰ <https://www.high-tech-gruenderfonds.de> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

¹¹ <http://www.germaninnovation.org> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

¹² <http://www.bpifrance.fr/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

¹³ <http://www.innovateuk.org/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

¹⁴ <https://www.ttgiv.org.tr/> (accessed: 29.08.2018)

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